

Research Article

Exploring Communication Dynamics at an Engineering Company: An Interview-Based Study

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Abstract

Communication is the vital exchange of information between people, groups, or places through words or mediums that help understanding. It is essential in various aspects of life, especially in professional interactions. Communication dynamics show various aspects of a workplace depending on its communication culture, challenges, and flow of communication in the company. The researchers aim to examine how communication dynamics influence employee engagement, the role of communication culture in shaping organizational behaviour, and the flow of communication through different hierarchical levels. The study employed a qualitative approach to investigate communication dynamics within an engineering company. Through in-depth interviews with seven employees representing various roles, data was collected using a structured questionnaire. Moreover, utilizing the thematic analysis to identify the data's recurring themes provides insight into organizational communication dynamics. Noticeably, there is an exchange of information and ideas, with its circular nature, signifying the dynamic interaction where feedback and mutuality are prevalent. This study aims to ascertain the prevailing communication model within an engineering company by analyzing the gathered data meticulously and interpreting its implications. Thus, the engineering company understudy has adopted the Osgood-Schramm model, a model proposed by Charles E. Osgood and Wilbur Schramm in 1954. Lastly, this study aspires to provide recommendations for improving communication dynamics within the company. Hence, this research underscored the importance of prioritizing face-to-face communication and bolstering leadership skills among project supervisors. Moreover, implementing these strategies is crucial for ensuring both project success and organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: Communication Dynamics, Osgood-Schramm Model, Organizational Behavior, Hierarchical Levels.

1. Introduction

Communication constitutes the actionable dissemination of information from one individual, collective, or locale to another through written or spoken language or a medium that provides a means of understanding. It plays a crucial role across diverse spheres of human activity, notably within professional engagement. Effective communication is essential for aligning workers, facilitating understanding, and achieving organizational goals (Razak *et al.*, 2019). Meaningful and effective communication within the workplace is governed by the capacity of parties to comprehend one another and make suitable responses. This study delves into the communication dynamics at an engineering company, a prominent construction company recognized for its innovative projects and commitment to excellence. Studying the communication practices of the engineering organization can provide civil engineering students with practical knowledge and skills directly applicable to their academic and professional pursuits.

The firm understudy is a construction firm established in 1993 and integrated in 2005. The company has demonstrated remarkable growth and success, completing nearly 100 projects with an unwavering commitment to excellence. Achieving ISO certification further underscores their dedication to quality and professionalism in the construction industry. It is a preferred company in the construction industry with a particular focus and emphasis on delivering quality professional services to its clients. This study was conducted to comprehend the communication dynamics, including the flow, challenges, and cultural aspects

within an engineering company. Hence, this study aspires to provide recommendations on how to improve communication dynamics. Through systematic analysis, we endeavour to identify prevalent issues, thereby facilitating the formulation of pertinent suggestions for improvement. The study employed a qualitative approach to investigate communication dynamics within the engineering company. Through in-depth interviews with seven employees representing various roles, data was collected using a structured questionnaire. Thematic analysis was utilized to identify recurring themes in the gathered data, providing insight into organizational communication dynamics.

2. Review of Related Literature

This section provides a summary of the literature that is relevant to the research topic at hand. The issues were thematically organized as follows: (1) Communication barrier, (2) Communication effects on job performance, and (3) Workplace hierarchy.

2.1. Communication Barrier

Communication barriers encompass factors that impede the effective delivery of messages from communicators to the intended recipients at the appropriate moment or hinder receivers from promptly receiving the intended message (Martic, 2023). According to Baldikov (2022), language and cultural differences are the most common challenges or barriers to effective communication. Misinterpretations of verbal and nonverbal cues can create conflicts that negatively impact team cohesion. In addition, determining the appropriate tools and communication channels presents a critical hurdle in achieving practical communication goals. One barrier to communication that leads to misunderstanding and conflict is the interference or distortion during the transfer of information across the medium or channel of communication (Obonadhuze *et al.*, 2021). According to the study of Yusof and Rahmat (2020), communication is essential in the workplace; they highlighted the environmental and personal barriers. The environmental barrier refers to the need for more time for careful thinking, which can lead to improper message structure and interpretation. On the other hand, the personal barrier refers to the fear of power and the inharmonious relationship between supervisor and subordinate. The personal barrier is the belief that employees cannot voice their opinions or question their seniors, which can hinder effective communication. Furthermore, Yusof and Rahmat (2020) also stated that the lack of empathy allows individuals to see the world through another's eyes and understand their colleagues' emotional states.

2.1.1. Lack of Communication

Whenever one party misinterprets or misconceives the words or actions of another, it can lead to the emergence of conflict. Ineffective communication in the workplace can be exasperating and result in diminished performance, weakened teamwork, decreased morale, and, ultimately, reduced profits (McQuerrey, 2019). A significant cause of postponements for a building endeavour is a result of poor communication among construction partners (Suleiman, 2022). As an article written by Appalachian Insights (2017), conflict within teams poses a significant obstacle to effective collaboration. Poor communication is a prominent contributor to such conflict, stemming from various causes beyond stress alone. Working within a group dynamic introduces diverse personalities and backgrounds, further complicating matters. Individuals within these groups may approach situations and solutions differently, often influenced by a belief in the superiority of their ideas or methods, even when alternative perspectives may be equally valid.

2.1.2. Physical Barriers

Clear communication is essential for the success of construction projects. Comprehending the value of clear and concise communication in construction is critical. Gratis (2022) elucidated that any physical object impeding communication, apart from cognitive barriers, qualifies as a tangible obstruction requiring resolution. Such impediments encompass barriers, wall distance between individuals, and background noise. Communication is vital in construction projects, but the industry's complexity can create barriers, compromising efficiency and precipitating costly errors. As an article from utilities supported, construction sites characterized by noisy and chaotic environments pose challenges for clear and concise communication. Communication breakdowns can occur on-site due to the distance between individuals, resulting in noise interference. According to an article from potential unearthed, noise- interruptions, distraction from ongoing activities, distortions of sound, internal noise, and inclusions of irrelevant material-distorts messages, hindering their intended understanding.

2.1.3. Language Differences

Language plays a dual role in human relationships: it serves as the primary means of communication, facilitating the creation of relationships, yet it can also act as a barrier, leading to division and distance

among people. These barriers emerge when the message is encoded or decoded into words and ideas. They can cause misunderstandings, resulting in disagreements, dissatisfaction, offense, violence, wasted time, effort, money, and even lives (Buarquob, 2019). Language is significantly essential in shaping social constructs of gender, as Eckert and McConnell-Ginet highlighted in their 2013 work. The way individuals are socialized into specific genders influences their use of language. This socialization process shapes the words they choose and their tone, style, and even nonverbal communication patterns, allowing space for miscommunication due to cultural and gender differences.

2.1.4. Culture and Gender

The growing significance of cultural and gender diversity in communication is becoming increasingly crucial for businesses due to its multifaceted relevance (Ceglarska, *et al.*, 2008). It forms the core of numerous organizational functions and global interactions (Harris and Moran, 2000, p.76). However, despite the benefits of diversity, organizations often need help in intercultural communication. Cultural communication barriers are the challenges arising when people from different cultures interact. These barriers are frequently highly complex, and as previously stated, they are based on the values and beliefs of specific groups (Cafarella, 2010).

Gender influences communication and its effectiveness. Men and women communicate differently. Genç (2017), states that different genders transfer and interpret information differently affecting their communications' effectiveness. Gender also influences how people perceive messages, what messages they send, and how they comprehend them, and this was supported by Ceglarska, *et al.*, (2008), who stated that communication within working teams could become more complex due to the varying mindsets and behavioural habits between male and female team members.

2.2. Effects of Communication on Job Performance

Practical communication abilities are indispensable for success in the contemporary, collaboration-oriented professional sphere. In an organization, employees play a crucial role similar to brain cells. At the same time, communication acts as the vital nervous system that transmits information and facilitates shared understanding among key organizational stakeholders (Goutam, 2013, p.88). With this, effective communication is crucial to successful and satisfactory job performance, as proved by skilled communicators who may establish bonds with coworkers and business partners, allowing them to finish projects productively and without delays. Furthermore, the success of building firms depends on the competence and efficiency of relationships between workers, subcontractors, engineers, clients, experts, and governing bodies (Jimoh, 2012). Poor communication is a common issue in large construction projects and is commonly cited as the primary cause of project failures (Suleiman, 2022).

Vague communication objectives, inadequate reporting mechanisms, ambiguous communication methods, insufficient communication among project stakeholders, variations in language, and discrimination can cause communication incompetence (Tipili *et al.*, 2014). This is further proved by Goutam (2013), who states that a lack of communication leads to errors and delayed due dates and causes many other significant workplace difficulties, including low motivation levels and poor job performance. Delays resulting from poor communication include errors in communication routes, reluctant movement of information, inaccurate interpretation, reworks, and more (Dainty *et al.*, 2007; Love and Li, 2000; Sambasivan and Soon, 2007; Tipili *et al.*, 2014). Construction firms in several countries like Saudi Arabia, Palestine, and Norway have poor workplace communication as the primary implication for cost and schedule overruns (Alhomidan, 2013; Omran and Suleiman, 2016; Zidane and Andersen, 2018).

2.2.1. Leadership Competency

The significance of communication skills as one of the components of interpersonal proficiency has been widely researched in connection to leadership (Madlock, 2008; Sager *et al.*, 2015; Westerman *et al.*, 2018). Communication breakdowns on construction sites can be attributed to a lack of leadership capabilities (Brookins, 2020). Project supervisors' expertise in coping with change and communication skills are critical to accomplishing any building endeavour (Hyväri, 2007). According to the study of Dauber and Tavernier (2011), inappropriate treatment by superiors can lead to various coping strategies, such as resistance, isolation, and distraction. Ineffective leadership can result in frustration, worse collaboration, and high psychological stress. Understanding the mechanism and consequences of ineffective leadership is crucial for effective leadership. Leadership is crucial in fostering employee involvement and engagement within an organization. Through effective communication, a leader can motivate employees to attain the organization's goal and inspire a deliberate and focused team effort to achieve it (Goutam, 2013, p.87). Additionally,

competent management leadership can produce a highly engaged workforce in an organization (Olukpe *et al.*, 2022).

2.2.2. Employee Involvement

One of the measures to enhance employees' work efficiency is actively participating in the organizational process. Employee engagement is always related to successful communication among employees and people in charge of the decision-making processes (Biryanto *et al.*, 2018). Lack of communication in the workforce is listed as one of the major factors hindering project progression. As stated by specialists, construction sites often need help with adequate communication caused of excluded workers, insufficiently trained employees, unclear objectives and responsibilities, and limited feedback (Brookins, 2020). Additionally, as emphasized by Enshassi *et al.*, (2009), the risk of construction conflicts should be an encouragement to stress the importance of practical discourse to foster rapport amongst building project groups. With this, all parties, leaders, and employees must enhance communication methodologies and strategies.

2.3. Workplace Hierarchy

2.3.1. Advantages of Workplace Hierarchy

An article entitled "Business Organisation Structure", published by NIBUSINESSINFO.CO.UK (<https://www.nibusinessinfo.co.uk/>), stated that the advantages of a hierarchical structure in businesses are numerous and significant. By establishing clear lines of authority and reporting, hierarchical structures facilitate streamlined decision-making processes and promote organizational cohesion. Furthermore, they contribute to a clearer understanding of employee roles and responsibilities, fostering increased productivity and collaboration. Organizations benefit from hierarchical structures in many ways. Employees are provided with clear career paths, development opportunities, and motivation. Hierarchical structures also allow for specialization and expertise development, which leads to improved performance and innovation. Close supervision and support of employees is made possible by a narrow span of managerial control, contributing to organizational success. Finally, hierarchical structures foster a culture of loyalty to teams, departments, and the organization, increasing employees' sense of belonging and unity. Given these benefits, hierarchical organizational structures continue to be a critical component of effective business management.

2.3.2. Disadvantages of Workplace Hierarchy

A company's hierarchical structure, which is rigidly organized, can seriously impede collaboration because it frequently limits collaboration within individual teams and discourages cross-functional communication. As a result, work is done in divisions, disregarding the company's overall objectives. Because approvals must go through multiple levels of the hierarchy, decision-making takes longer, affecting team morale and productivity. As an article from a website from Indeed suggested, having a hierarchical structure leads to slower decision-making, communication barriers, and departmental rivalry (Indeed Editorial Team, 2021a). Communication problems are common between employees in different departments who may find it difficult to coordinate because of operational differences and vertically between hierarchy levels where messages may be misplaced or altered. In addition, the hierarchical structure creates a competitive environment where teams strive independently to fulfil the objectives of their respective departments instead of cooperating to accomplish the organization's overarching goal. Moreover, the hierarchical structure creates a competitive environment where teams strive independently to fulfil the objectives of their respective departments instead of cooperating to accomplish the organization's overall goal, which hinders productive teamwork (Hermitte, 2023).

3. Theoretical Framework

The study's theoretical foundation is based on Steve Neale's genre theory, which defined the genre as "specific variations of the interplay of codes." According to this theory, genres describe communication as a numerous understanding that needs in-depth investigation to grasp the idea of it thoroughly. This theory also states that it can be applied in different fields and circumstances. According to Masduki and Zakaria (2020), engineering genres in communication include presentations, progress reports, and decision-making. These genres are essential to this study as this will provide the importance of communication in a specific field and its functionality to the organization. Furthermore, this theory will help the researcher see the diversity of a field in the essence of communication. The genre theory, as it relates to this study, as it does not separate from the person who uses it—will allow the researchers to see the created dynamics of the respondents interacting within the organization. As each field has a different genre, the researchers who will mainly focus on engineering will see the elements in the organizational setting needed for the organization's prosperity and the members themselves.

4. Methodology

4.1. Research Method

The researchers employed the qualitative research approach to investigate the communication dynamics of an engineering company.

To find out how employees communicate with one another, the researchers conducted in-depth interviews with workers. A qualitative research technique called an in-depth interview is used to learn specifics about a subject and delve into informants' opinions, experiences, and viewpoints. This method allows or generates comprehensive data that personal narrative sheds light on an individual's viewpoint, personal experiences, emotions, and interpretation of a particular subject or problem. Moreover, the study employed a structured interview, a method of data collection involving asking questions in a predetermined sequence to obtain information on a particular topic (George and Merkus, 2023).

The researchers utilized a structured interview-style questionnaire to gather information through interviews. The questionnaire has 12 questions that are modified depending on the goals of this research. Its purpose was to investigate the communication dynamics within an engineering company.

The interview will be recorded, and researchers will ask for the participant's consent before recording. These interviews provided an opportunity for respondents to express their perspectives. Each interview typically lasted 5 to 15 minutes. All recordings were gathered, transcribed, and organized into themes following the interviews. This data served as the foundation for subsequent analysis and interpretation. Thanks to this study methodology, the researchers can offer far more thorough information, which will also help us understand the communication dynamics within the organization.

4.2. Sample and Sampling Procedure

The participants will be chosen using purposive sampling, explicitly targeting individuals from an engineering company, aligning with the study's focus on understanding organizational communication dynamics. According to Campbell *et al.*, (2020), purposive sampling disregards all unnecessary sampling, making sure to have a specific possible final sample, given the aims and objectives of the study, which will hold different views and essential ideas and issues that will benefit the study. Thus, the respondents of this study are company employees. There are 7(seven) employees ranging from 23 to 54 years old, each occupying a distinct role within the organizational hierarchy. These positions encompass a range of roles, including Senior Manager, Project Engineer, Office Engineer, Foreman, Rigger, Welder, and HR Supervisor. Notably, each position is represented equally, accounting for 14.29% of the respondents, indicating a balanced sampling across various job functions.

4.3. Ethical Considerations

When conducting any study, adhering to ethical principles such as maintaining and safeguarding the privacy and confidentiality of participants' shared experiences, respecting intellectual property rights, and minimizing potential harm is essential (Ravitch and Carl, 2016). Thus, agreement from the study's participants is required before data collection can start. Participants will be required to give their consent formally. At the same time, the researchers attest to their understanding of their right to access their information, revoke consent at any time, and agree to participate in the study. During the informed consent phase, the researcher and the subjects must reach an agreement. The Philippines passed the Data Privacy Act in 2012, establishing thorough and rigorous privacy regulations "to preserve the basic human right of privacy, communication, and free flow of information in order to foster innovation and progress." (Republic Act. No. 10173 Ch. 1, Sec. 2). The assurances extend beyond simply protecting the participants' names and encompass avoiding the use of self-identifying remarks and content. Participants' identities are kept private or anonymous. By following this ethical consideration, the researcher will have secured the participant's right to autonomy. When followed, informed consent can help to protect personal liberty and integrity. In this context, the researcher will need to explain the study and its purpose before commencing data collection. The subjects will also be informed about the proceedings.

4.4. Mode of Analysis

The researchers utilized thematic analysis to determine the theme of the responses provided by the respondents to each of the prepared questions and to ascertain the precise nature of their answers. Thematic analysis is the examination of qualitative data. It is commonly used with texts such as interviews or transcripts. The researcher thoroughly examines the data to identify common themes, which could include topics, ideas, and recurring patterns of meaning (Caulfield, 2019). It is a data description method that also

includes interpretation when choosing codes and creating themes. Researchers use thematic analysis to gain insight into a data set's experiences, thoughts, and behaviors (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Furthermore, it is essential to have enough data for the researcher to explore the communication dynamics within the engineering company. Using tables would make the analysis part of the data more organized and accessible.

5. Result and Discussion

This chapter presents the gathered data and interpretation of findings from interviews with seven (7) workers at an engineering company. The results are introduced through themes that exhibit the overall evaluation and interpretation of the data collected from the participants.

5.1. Employee's Profile Summary

Table 1. Employee's profile summary.

Participant	Age	Position	Working years
Participant 1	54	Senior manager	30 years
Participant 2	28	Project engineer	7 years
Participant 3	23	Office engineer	8 months
Participant 4	40	Civil works foreman	15 years
Participant 5	52	Rigger	25 years
Participant 6	29	Welder	3 years
Participant 7	45	HR supervisor	18 years

Table 1 shows the number of respondents, age, position, and working years who participated in an interview conducted at the company. 7 (seven) respondents ranging from 23-54 years old and working years of 3-30 years, including their company position such as senior manager, project engineer, office engineer, civil works foreman, rigger, welder, and HR supervisor.

5.2. Communication Flow

5.2.1. Flow of Information in Organizational Hierarchies

Hierarchical structures provide a framework that fosters organization. They establish clear lines of authority and responsibility, promoting unity and cohesion among team members. This structure ensures that communication flows efficiently from management downwards, disseminating vital information and directives to all levels of the organization. It enables decision-making to be delegated to those best suited to make the necessary choices while ensuring accountability (Varghese, 2023). Moreover, hierarchical systems facilitate accountability, as each individual understands their role within the larger framework and their specific responsibilities. Thus, hierarchical communication is a cornerstone of effective organizational functioning; ensuring that goals are communicated effectively and tasks are carried out with clarity and purpose. One respondent highlighted the practice of conducting meetings to cascade functions from management to engineers and eventually to the workers. This systematic approach ensures that every organization member is fully informed about their assigned tasks. Moreover, higher-level leaders take proactive steps to ensure their team members understand these tasks clearly. This process facilitates efficient communication and promotes accountability and alignment within the organization. By ensuring that tasks are understood at every level, leaders empower their teams to perform effectively and contribute to the organization's overall success. This commitment to clarity and comprehension reflects a culture of transparency and collaboration, essential for achieving shared goals and driving continuous improvement.

5.2.2. Communication Channels

5.2.2.1. Digital Connectivity

In the context of evolving work environments and the shifting dynamics of careers, the advent of technology serves as a beacon of connectivity and efficiency. The rapid dissemination of information, from management down to the workforce, has become increasingly seamless. Technology has made it easier for people to connect regardless of their location (Keshav, 2023). Applications like Viber have emerged as pivotal tools, not only for maintaining connections with clients but also for fostering communication within organizations. Furthermore, using smartphones as primary communication devices underscores the blend of accessibility and convenience technology brings to the modern professional landscape. This digital transformation facilitates a more connected, responsive, and agile work environment, adapting to the challenges and opportunities of the times. Given this information, four (4) out of seven (7) respondents mainly depend on using technology as their communication medium. Specifically, they utilize the phone call and messaging functionalities offered by the application known as Viber. Technology improves communication by making it

easier, faster, and more efficient. It enables you to track conversations and thus improve customer service (Patel, 2021).

5.2.2.2. On-Site Discussions

In an engineering organization, the value of face-to-face communication cannot be overstated. Ensuring that management's communication is clearly understood and accurately implemented is essential. It enables more than just speaking because both the speaker and the listener(s) can observe and respond to body language and expression (Grossman, 2022). Direct discussions offer an irreplaceable platform for clarifying tasks, allowing immediate feedback, and resolving ambiguities. Assembling each morning for a conversation before work begins is particularly effective. It addresses issues and concerns in real time and fosters community and collective responsibility among team members. Engaging in such daily meetings ensures that all team members are aligned with the day's objectives and are fully prepared to tackle their tasks, clearly understanding their roles and responsibilities. This approach underscores the importance of interpersonal communication in maintaining the efficiency and cohesion of engineering teams, ensuring that all members are informed, engaged, and motivated. Our respondents conduct on-site discussions before working on and doing their assigned tasks.

5.3. Communication Strategies

Table 2. Communication strategies.

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Verbal communication	6	85.71%
Non-verbal communication	1	14.28%
Written communication	4	57.14%
Visual communication	1	14.28%

The data indicating that 6 out of 7 respondents favor verbal communication as their primary communication strategy highlights the strong preference for spoken interactions among the surveyed individuals. Given the need for on-site coordination, face-to-face discussions and verbal instructions are favored for quick decision-making and clarity.

Moreover, four (4) respondents also chose written communication as one of their communication strategies. This could indicate the importance of documentation in the construction industry. Written communication, such as project plans, safety manuals, and reports, ensures that information is recorded accurately and can be referred to when needed, especially for legal or compliance purposes.

One (1) respondent utilizes visual communication, suggesting an appreciation for visual aids like blueprints or digital renderings in construction planning. Visual communication aids in conveying complex design concepts effectively to different project stakeholders.

One (1) respondent selects nonverbal communication as their primary strategy due to its effectiveness and practicality in their specific work setting. This underscores the adaptability of communication strategies based on role and environment demands, highlighting the importance of selecting the most suitable means for optimal outcomes. Different organizational roles or levels may require varying communication approaches.

5.4. Communication and Collaboration

5.4.1. Collaborative Teamwork

5.4.1.1. Project Meeting

The participants said that the company conducts project meetings for consistent collaboration. Regular project meetings are held to review progress, address issues, and make decisions regarding construction projects. Project meetings are vital in fostering cooperation, leadership, and effective decision-making. Well-planned meetings at critical milestones are essential for keeping projects on course (Lyn, 2023). These meetings involve stakeholders such as project managers, engineers, architects, subcontractors, and clients.

5.4.1.2. Toolbox Meeting

All participants stated that they regularly conduct toolbox meetings every morning. Before starting work each day, construction teams often meet briefly to discuss the day's tasks, safety measures, and any challenges or concerns. These hurdles ensure that everyone is on the same page and aware of critical

information. As Deltek stated in their published article, regular toolbox talks can enhance team communication and collaboration, fostering a safer and more efficient work setting in construction sites (<https://www.deltek.com/>)

5.4.2. Frequency of Communicative Interactions

5.4.2.1. Persistent Interaction

Many construction endeavors involve intricate processes and require extensive collaboration. Consequently, effectively organizing and managing communication within these projects poses a significant hurdle (Zerjav and Ceric, 2009). In the construction firm, team communication is structured and consistent. Three (3) participants indicated they hold meetings thrice a week to discuss project updates, ensuring everyone is aligned on progress and challenges. Meanwhile, another four participants mentioned regular meetings, emphasizing the ongoing nature of communication within the teams. This frequent interaction underscores the collaborative approach taken within the company, which is vital for the dynamic and evolving nature of construction projects.

5.5. Leadership Style in Communication

5.5.1. Leader's Communication Styles on Employee's Performance

5.5.1.1. Positive Impact on Employee's Performance

Leadership encourages people to contribute confidently toward a shared objective (Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019). An essential part of being a leader is effectively communicating with subordinates (Muslih, 2020) because it positively affects workplace fulfillment and organizational success (Avolio *et al.*, 2004, Dasborough, 2006, Mastrangelo *et al.*, 2014; Paliszkievicz *et al.*, 2015). Communicating effectively is a critical component of project-driven leadership and is acknowledged as vital to efficient project oversight (Yap *et al.*, 2017). Relaying information successfully on construction sites is one of the most essential strategies to ensure a building project succeeds and without errors. The senior manager at the engineering company on resolving conflicts and addressing problems stated, *"Kino-call yung attention kung sino [ang] mga involved, kung ano yung lesson learned na dapat sa mga susunod na same situation eh macorrect na kaagad. Para hindi na paulit ulit yung mga mistakes na na-encounter pagdating sa miscommunication."* (*"Attention is drawn to who is involved and what lessons should be learned so that corrections can be made immediately in the next similar situation. So that the mistakes encountered in miscommunication are not repeated repeatedly."*). As a leader, being equipped with communication skills allows for a more motivated workforce, which boosts morale, work enthusiasm, efficiency, and performance. As an interviewee stated on how leaders' communication styles influence employees' performance, *"Mas nagiging comfortable yung atmosphere sa loob ng company [at] mas nagiging open [kami] sa isa't isa, kaya mas maayos yung performance and nami-minimize yung mga conflicts."* (*"The atmosphere inside the company becomes more comfortable, and we become more open to each other, which improves performance and minimizes conflicts."*) This demonstrates that a skilled leader who communicates efficiently with their staff can enhance the success of projects, while also mitigating or resolving a range of challenges that may arise during construction projects.

5.5.2. Leadership Strategies and Employee Adoption

5.5.2.1. Clear Communication

Clear communication is crucial for organizational success. It facilitates efficient decision-making, prevents conflicts, and enhances productivity. It helps employees understand their concerns, improves processes, and builds a strong reputation. Transparent and effective communication practices attract top talent and gain stakeholder trust, ensuring a thriving business environment (Team, 2023). Clear communication is the lifeblood of every organization. Clearly and concisely communicating concepts, guidelines, and comments is essential in such a dynamic and complicated setting, where projects usually involve multiple stakeholders and complex technical details.

All seven (7) participants stated that they adopted clear communication as one of their strategies. Transparent and efficient communication guarantees that all employees are aware of their roles and duties minimizes the possibility of mistakes or misunderstandings and encourages teamwork and creativity. It promotes a working environment of trust and accountability, which empowers employees to take on obstacles head-on and accomplish their objectives. In their organization, effective communication is a desired quality and an essential requirement for advancing their goals and producing top-notch outputs.

5.5.2.2. Open Communication

Open communication is the transparent, honest, and dependable sharing of information between people in a workplace. It helps employees express their thoughts, feelings, and plans clearly, eliminating aggressive

words and nonverbal cues. With open communication, internal systems can improve, leading to problems like duplicate work or a lack of task completion (Miller, 2022). All seven (7) participants affirmed that they employed open communication as one of their strategies. Open communication is the foundation of success in organizations; it fosters an atmosphere where ideas are exchanged openly, criticism is welcomed, and issues are quickly resolved. They promote open communication between managers, stakeholders, and employees inside their firm. Their company encourages creativity, finds solutions to problems, and builds teamwork through open communication. This openness fosters unity and trust among employees, empowering them to confidently overcome obstacles and accomplish their goals. They have an open line of communication throughout their organization, which helps them maintain excellence over time and develop continuously.

5.5.2.3. Recognition and Feedback

Feedback is usually viewed as a negative. However, recognition is an essential form of feedback. Expressing employee appreciation is a potent method for making them feel valued, extending beyond merely recognizing positive outcomes, performance, or conduct. When employees are recognized and appreciated for their individual contributions, they become more connected to their work, team, and organization (Wickham, 2023). Accepting constructive criticism and good comments is essential to their organization's development. Recognition of desired actions and acknowledgment of accomplishments inspires their employees to keep doing well. Negative feedback, on the other hand, draws attention to areas that need work and offers valuable insight for growth and learning. Their organization fosters continuous development and responsibility by transparently acknowledging accomplishments and addressing areas of concern. This approach encourages excellence in their organization.

5.5.2.4. Clarification

Every piece of information gathered undergoes thorough clarification. Workers consistently inquire multiple times to ensure they fully grasp their assigned tasks. Simultaneously, workers take the initiative to clarify any ambiguities with engineers or HR regarding their assigned tasks. Clarification is significant; it is required for effective communication whenever there is ambiguity about what was said. It ensures that you understand everything and demonstrate to your communication partner that you are listening and actively participating (Thompson, 2020). As one participant stated, "*Hangga't hindi ako sigurado na naiintindihan ng worker ang trabaho, hindi ako aalis. Kung kailangan ipaliwanag, ipapaliwanag ko ulit.*" This meticulous approach to clarification underscores a commitment to precision and understanding within the organization. It minimizes the risk of misunderstandings and fosters a culture of proactive communication and accountability. By encouraging open dialogue and continuous clarification, the organization ensures that tasks are executed with clarity and purpose, driving efficiency and effectiveness across all levels.

5.5.2.5. Teamwork

All participants stated that teamwork is a fundamental strategy for their collaboration. Collaborating with others to achieve shared objectives is crucial in the professional setting, as it brings people together. Its significance is particularly noticeable in engineering company where the intricacy of projects demands teamwork and specialized knowledge. As it fosters a vibrant, resilient company culture, teamwork increases productivity and project outcomes. In engineering organizations, where employees' accumulated knowledge and dedication determine performance, teamwork is the cornerstone of achievement and growth.

As Full Blast Hydraulics stated, working in a group enables workers to gain from one another's expertise and experience, promoting support and communication inside the workshop. According to the respondents, mutual understanding is crucial, particularly in situations where disputes emerge. As a cooperative organization, don't point the finger at anyone when disagreements arise (www.fullblasthydraulics.com).

5.5.3. Leader's Navigating Conflicts

5.5.3.1. Open Dialogue

The participants emphasized that, as they take up leadership positions in an office or on-site environment, open communication is one of their main strategies for resolving conflicts at work. They understand that fostering an atmosphere of open communication enables team members to voice their opinions and concerns in a respectful and safe setting. Facilitating open dialogue allows leaders to establish an environment in which disagreements can be freely discussed and settled, which in turn promotes cooperation and understanding within the team.

Some of their statements are:

"pag hindi sila natatakot magsabi nung mga opinion nila, magkakaroon ng mas better na decision-making and magkakaroon ng madandang daloy nag pagresolve ng problema" ("If they are not afraid to express their opinions, there will be better decision-making and a better flow of problem-solving.")

"mas naiidentify namin yung root cause ng problema pag naririnig namin side ng bawat isa." ("We better identify the root cause of the problem when we hear each other's side.")

5.5.3.2. Active Listening

All of the participants also used active listening as a conflict-resolution technique. Participants were able to increase understanding, promote more effective communication, and solve problems more successfully by actively listening to one another's viewpoints and concerns.

Some of their response is:

"Makinig muna, un ang unang una na dapat gawin. Pakinggan ang sasabihin ng lahat ng mga involved, para malaman ang buong story." (Listening first is essential. Hear out what everyone involved has to say to understand the whole story.)

5.6. Organization Culture

5.6.1. Cultural Norms around Communication

The data presented have been meticulously gathered via keen observation and insightful interviews.

5.6.1.1. Dominant Language of Communication

The results show that Tagalog is the most common language used for communication in the construction company. According to the study, the vast majority of the employees-if not all of them-interact primarily in Filipino, with English serving as a secondary language. This preference for Tagalog may be explained by the cultural background of the labor force, as Filipinos are more comfortable speaking in their native tongue in professional contexts like construction, where instructions and complex technical terms are common. Although Tagalog is the main language spoken, being good at English is still very important. When communicating with clients, suppliers, or advisors from different locations, employees may need to use their strong English language skills to ensure that everyone is clear on what needs to be done on a project and can understand one another. Therefore, while Tagalog helps with communication and camaraderie inside the company, being good at English is still important for talking to people outside and keeping the company competitive in the worldwide construction market.

5.6.1.2. Straightforward and Direct

All participants encouraged direct communication, especially when giving directions. This implies that they prioritize efficiency and comprehension in their communication style, placing a high value on conciseness and clarity in their interactions."

5.6.1.3. Formal and Informal

The majority of participants preferred using formal communication channels while inside the office, including email exchanges and in-person meetings with employees. However, they emphasized the importance of informal communication methods for communication outside the office, primarily on-site. Participants stated that informal communication on the job site fosters a better understanding of tasks without putting too much pressure on employees. This laid-back environment facilitates more open communication and better understanding, improving task comprehension and encouraging a collaborative work environment. An article in Pelago claims that informal communication makes it easier for managers and staff to share important details in an efficient way. By acknowledging both formal and informal contexts, organizations can tailor their communication strategies to enhance task clarity and employee engagement. This well-rounded approach not only ensures efficient conveyance of information but also nurtures a harmonious and encouraging workplace environment (<https://www.pelagohealth.com>).

5.7. Conflicts

5.7.1. Conflict Resolution in Company Communication

5.7.1.1. Open Communication

Out of the seven participants, seven (7) support open communication as the first step in resolving conflicts. They emphasize the importance of establishing a secure atmosphere for employees to express their concerns

without hesitance. The key to a successful resolution of conflicts is to address them immediately and directly with all parties involved.

5.7.1.2. Constructive Feedback and Correction

As one (1) of our participants stated, *"Pag nagkamali sila, ituro mo sakanila yung tamang way, kasi lahat naman nagkakamali."* ("If they make a mistake, guide them towards the right way because everyone makes mistakes.") Constructive criticism and advice are offered instead of immediately fixing mistakes, allowing people to think through and grow from their mistakes. According to an article published by Indeed, rather than being critical, the feedback is helpful and constructive, providing concrete examples of improvements that will aid in professional development (Indeed Editorial Team. 2021b).

5.7.1.3. No Blame Culture and Root Cause Breakdown

All seven (7) participants emphasized the value of creating a supportive and nonjudgmental environment and resolving conflicts without putting blame. They stress how important it is to look into the issue and determine its underlying causes by weighing all relevant information and factors. As one participant stated that *"Hindi pwede na one sided lang, pag nagka problem, aalimin lahat. Alamin pinagmulan, pakinggan both sides ng story. And analyze kung saan nagkaroon ng pagkukulang."* ("It cannot be one-sided. When a problem arises, everyone should be heard. Understand the root cause, listen to both sides of the story, and analyze where the shortcomings occurred.")

5.8. Generational Differences

5.8.1. Communication Preferences across Generations in the Workplace

Table 3. Communication preferences across generations in the workplace frequency.

Participant	Age	Generation	Do you find it challenging to communicate with employees of different ages or generations?
Participant 1	54	Gen X	No
Participant 2	28	Millennials	No
Participant 3	23	Gen Z	No
Participant 4	40	Millennials	No
Participant 5	52	Gen X	No
Participant 6	29	Millennials	No
Participant 7	45	Gen X	No

Based on the findings, the participants across different age groups and generations are relatively easy to communicate with employees of different ages or generations. This suggests a level of comfort and adaptability in communication styles among individuals in the workplace, regardless of age differences. It could also indicate that workplaces have adapted their communication practices to be inclusive and accommodating to various generations. Some of their responses are the following:

"Ako yung nagbibigay instruction, oo mag aadjust ka pero magadjust rin sila. Pakita mo na may respeto ka sa tao, rerespetuhin ka rin nila." ("I'm the one who gives the instructions. Yes, you will adjust, but they will also adjust. Show that you respect people, and they will respect you, too.")

"Yung level ng communication is ibababa namin kung hanggang saan level ng kanilang pagkakaintindi. May adjustment lagi" ("We will lower the level of communication to what level of their understanding. There is always an adjustment.")

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of the findings, the conclusions drawn from the findings, and the corresponding recommendations. This study is taken with the general objective of determining the communication dynamics at the engineering company understudy.

6.1. Summary of Findings

In light of the study, the following conclusions have been drawn:

6.1.1. Communication Channels

Digital connectivity has transformed communication channels in the modern workplace, enabling the quick spread of information via apps like Viber. In engineering organizations in particular, face-to-face discussions

are still very beneficial because they facilitate prompt feedback and task clarification. The preference for verbal communication is evidence of how effective it is at promoting clarity and prompt decision-making.

6.1.2. Collaborative Teamwork

Engineering projects require teamwork to be successful, and regular toolbox and project meetings provide an opportunity for efficient coordination and communication. Team members' continuous communication highlights the engineering company's collaborative approach, which is crucial for managing the changing nature of construction projects.

6.1.3. Leadership Style in Communication

Successful leadership techniques are essential for encouraging staff involvement and achieving organizational goals. Clear and open lines of communication are essential for promoting effective decision-making, avoiding conflicts, and boosting productivity. Employee accountability and development are encouraged by recognition and feedback systems. While teamwork promotes collaboration and the accomplishment of common goals, thorough clarification guarantees task comprehension and reduces misunderstandings. In addition, handling disagreements with open communication and attentive listening fosters comprehension and efficient problem-solving. Through the implementation of these strategies, organizations can establish a dynamic and encouraging work environment that fosters excellence and growth.

6.1.4. Organization Culture

Within the construction company, communication norms emphasize Tagalog as the primary language, with English proficiency also considered necessary for global competitiveness. The preference for direct communication emphasizes how important efficiency and clarity are. While formal means are preferred in-office, informal communication cultivates comprehension and cooperation on-site. Maintaining a healthy work environment that fosters productive communication and engagement can be achieved by striking a balance between formal and informal approaches.

6.1.5. Conflict Resolution

Engineering organizations' conflict resolution techniques revolve around three key elements: constructive criticism, open communication, and a blame-free environment. Effective conflict resolution and teamwork are dependent on promoting open communication, identifying the underlying causes of problems, and creating a supportive atmosphere. This study focuses on determining the current communication model of an engineering company by carefully examining the collected data and deriving conclusions from it. The engineering company has implemented the Osgood-Schramm Model, originally proposed by Charles E. Osgood and Wilbur Schramm in 1954. This model differs from traditional linear models as it illustrates communication as circular in nature. The sender and recipient in this model are always exchanging ideas and information. This circular nature indicates that communication is a dynamic interaction in which mutual understanding and feedback are essential components, rather than just a one-way transmission.

7. Recommendation

Based on the research's findings and conclusions, the following endorsements are recommended for each aspect:

7.1. Engineering Company

Beyond digital technology, the engineering company needs to understand the value of a variety of communication channels in today's fast-paced digital world. The researchers recommend that the organization give priority to in-person meetings and conversations. This approach helps to make tasks more clear, fosters teamwork and cooperation among team members, and encourages quick responses. This method encourages prompt responses, aids in clarifying tasks, and promotes teamwork and cooperation among team members.

In an engineering company, conveying task details can be challenging without concrete examples. The researchers recommend using examples to visualize tasks, aiding workers in understanding their assigned responsibilities more thoroughly. Providing tangible examples, whether through drawings, prototypes, or simulations, can bridge the gap between abstract concepts and practical execution. Examples can clarify complex concepts, including regulations. They are an excellent way to help readers and listeners (Murawski, 1999). Visualizing tasks enhances comprehension and ensures that workers have a precise reference point for their work, reducing the likelihood of misunderstandings or errors. Incorporating examples into task

explanations is essential for effective communication within an engineering company, enabling workers to grasp the intricacies of their assignments and contribute to the success of projects. While Tagalog serves as the primary language within the organization, it is imperative to recognize that proficiency in English is vital for effective external communication and to maintain its global competitiveness. Thus, the researchers suggest that the engineering company should provide language training or resources to ensure employees have the necessary English language skills.

The expertise of project supervisors in coping with change and their communication skills are critical to the success of any project. Failure to lead effectively can hurt staff and circumstances in the organizational environment. From the employee's viewpoint, inadequate leadership results in low levels of job satisfaction diminished commitment, and psychological distress (Tepper, 2000; Tepper *et al.*, 2011). Research suggests that the company should provide more comprehensive leadership training programs for project supervisors or employees with higher positions. The programs should concentrate on improving their skills in coping with change, effective communication, conflict resolution, and team motivation.

7.2. Construction Industry Professionals

The researchers recommend using these findings to structure communication with professionals or organizations. They also advise organizations to carefully select the appropriate channel for each communication scenario or business process, using this study as a guide. Selecting the appropriate communication channel facilitates efficient and effective interaction, ensuring precise message delivery and feedback. This approach saves time, improves understanding and relationships, and boosts business productivity and success.

7.3. Civil Engineering Students

Researchers recommend studying this work for civil engineering students to enhance their understanding of professional communication. This study offers guidance on effective communication practices for aspiring registered civil engineers.

8. Future Researchers

For future researchers, improving this research will make it more pleasing and trustworthy for readers. The researcher suggests expanding this study will be one way to do this, with more data gathering to validate the findings across different contexts or populations. This could involve conducting additional experiments or surveys to gather more comprehensive data, thereby increasing the quality of the results.

9. Limitations

This study covered the communication dynamics of an engineering company using an interview and observation approach. This study will investigate possible communication problems or challenges in the workplace that can affect the organization's success. It will also determine the different workplace communication processes or strategies employees use. The participants in this study exclusively consist of employees affiliated with the organization, with no involvement of external third parties. It is restricted to the communication dynamics within the company. It does not encompass external factors influencing communication within the broader construction industry or other industries. The study was conducted with a relatively small sample size drawn, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader populations. Furthermore, there are also time limitations for data collection, which may have restricted the breadth and depth of information gathered.

Declarations

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